

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some α -amino acids by butyltriphenylphosphonium dichromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of a series of nine α -amino acids by butyltriphenylphosphonium dichromate (BTPPD) in glacial acetic acid in the presence of toluene *p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH), leads to the formation of corresponding aldimines. The reactions are of first order with respect to BTPPD whereas the second order dependence is observed with respect to each the amino acid and hydrogen ion. The oxidation of perdeuteriogylicine showed the absence of a kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 1.01$ at 308 K). The reactions showed an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* substituent constants, the reaction constant being negative. The oxidation of alanine was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed using Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The analyses of solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. Suitable mechanisms for the oxidation process are postulated.

Keywords : α -Amino acid, kinetics, oxidation, correlation analysis, Cr^{VI} complex.

Introduction

Selective oxidation of organic compounds under non-aqueous conditions is an important transformation in synthetic organic chemistry. For this, a number of different chromium(VI) derivatives have been reported^{1,2}. Butyltriphenylphosphonium dichromate (BTPPD), a Cr^{VI} derivative, is reported to be a mild and selective oxidant³. It oxidizes amines to azo-compounds, thiols to disulphides and regenerates carbonyl compounds from their oximes. We have been interested in the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation by BTPPD and a few reports have already been emanated from our laboratory⁴⁻⁷. There seems to be no report on the mechanistic aspects of the oxidation of amino acids by BTPPD. We have, therefore, undertaken the present study and report here the kinetics of oxidation of a series of amino acids viz. glycine, α -alanine, phenylalanine, 2-aminobutanoic acid, norvaline, norleucine, valine, leucine and isoleucine by BTPPD in glacial acetic acid in the presence of toluene *p*-sulphonic acid, primarily to discuss the mechanistic aspects and secondly to study the correlation of structure and reactivity.

Results and discussion

The rates and other experimental data were obtained for all the amino acids. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of amino acid by BTPPD results in the formation of corresponding aldimines as the main product. Analyses of products and stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction.

The reactions were found to be of first order with respect to BTPPD. In individual kinetic runs, plots of log [BTPPD] versus time were linear ($r^2 > 0.995$). Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial concentration of BTPPD (Table 1). The reactions showed a second order dependence on the concentration of amino acid, as observed by the nearly constant values of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{amino acid}]^2$ (Table 1).

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of acid by BTPPD, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. In blank experiments, with the substrate absent, no noticeable consumption of BTPPD was observed. The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively. The rates of oxidation

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of alanine by BTPPD at 328 K

10^2 [Alanine] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^4 [BTPPD] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
0.9	5.0	1.0	0.35
1.5	5.0	1.0	1.01
3.0	5.0	1.0	4.08
4.5	5.0	1.0	8.97
6.0	5.0	1.0	16.2
9.0	5.0	1.0	32.0
13.5	5.0	1.0	73.3
9.0	8.0	1.0	33.1
9.0	10.0	1.0	34.6
9.0	20.0	1.0	31.8
9.0	30.0	1.0	32.8
13.5	5.0	1.0	75.0 ^a
13.5	5.0	1.0	73.9 ^b

^aContains 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile,

^bcontains 0.01 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

increase with an increase in acidity. The dependence on hydrogen ion concentration is of the form $k_{\text{obs}} = k [\text{H}^+]^2$, as observed by the nearly constant values of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{H}^+]^2$ (Table 2). The rates of oxidation of nine amino acids were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3).

Table 2. Effect of acidity on the oxidation of alanine by BTPPD

[Alanine] = 0.135 mol dm ⁻³ , [BTPPD] = 0.0005 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. 328 K						
[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.8	1.0
$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	0.75	2.89	6.53	18.1	46.2	73.2

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of amino acids (RCHNH₂COOH) by BTPPD

Subst.	$k_2 \times 10^3$ (dm ¹² mol ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
	298 K	308 K	318 K	328 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
H	5.39	9.28	14.7	24.6	38.2 ± 0.6	-161 ± 2	86.0 ± 0.5
Me	10.5	17.0	25.1	40.2	33.4 ± 0.8	-171 ± 2	84.3 ± 0.6
PhCH ₂	7.74	12.6	19.7	32.2	35.8 ± 0.6	-166 ± 2	85.1 ± 0.6
Et	11.8	19.0	28.0	44.2	32.8 ± 0.7	-172 ± 2	84.0 ± 0.5
Pr	12.1	19.4	28.4	44.9	32.5 ± 0.7	-173 ± 3	83.9 ± 0.6
Bu	12.6	20.0	29.2	46.0	32.1 ± 0.7	-174 ± 3	83.9 ± 0.6
<i>i</i> -Pr	13.7	21.7	31.3	48.9	31.5 ± 0.7	-176 ± 3	83.7 ± 0.6
<i>i</i> -Bu	12.4	19.7	28.7	45.5	32.2 ± 0.8	-174 ± 3	83.9 ± 0.6
<i>s</i> -Bu	14.1	22.3	31.8	49.9	31.2 ± 0.8	-176 ± 3	83.6 ± 0.7
Dgly	5.47	9.21	15.1	24.4	38.0 ± 0.2	-162 ± 1	85.9 ± 0.1
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	0.98	1.01	0.97	1.01			

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of perdeuteriogylicine (Dgly) was studied. The results recorded in Table 3 showed the absence of kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 1.01$ at 308 K).

Solvent effect : The oxidation of alanine by BTPPD was studied in nineteen organic solvents. The solubility of the reactants and the reaction of BTPPD with primary and secondary alcohols limited the choice of solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 4.

The entropies and enthalpies of activation of the oxidation of amino acids by BTPPD exhibited a good correlation ($r^2 = 0.9958$). The value of isokinetic temperature is 459 ± 11 . The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion⁸. However, Exner suggested an alternative method for establishing the isokinetic relationship. The Exner's plot between the values of $\log k_2$ at 298 K and at 328 K for the nine amino acids, is found to be linear (slope = 0.7373 ± 0.0039 ; $r^2 = 0.9998$). The value of isokinetic temperature, determined by Exner's method, is 457 ± 3 K. The two values of isokinetic temperature, determined by two different methods, match very well. A linear isokinetic relationship is, however, a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships⁶. It also implies that all the reactions, so correlated, follow a similar mechanism.

In acid media, amino acid exists as a mixture of the zwitterionic (A) and cationic (B) forms. Since, acetic acid is a weak acid and further the amino acid reacts to an electropositive oxidizing species, the reactive form of

Table 4. Effect of solvent on the oxidation of alanine by BTPPD at 328 K

Solvent	$k_2 \times 10^3$ ($\text{mol}^{-4} \text{dm}^{12}$ s^{-1})	Solvent	$k_2 \times 10^3$ ($\text{mol}^{-4} \text{dm}^{12}$ s^{-1})
Chloroform	8.82	Toluene	2.28
1,2-Dichloroethane	10.8	Acetophenone	14.2
Dichloromethane	10.4	Tetrahydrofuran	4.45
DMSO	40.2	<i>t</i> -BuOH	3.00
Acetone	9.75	Dioxane	4.60
Dimethylformamide	18.3	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	2.03
Butanone	6.83	Acetic acid	1.20
Nitrobenzene	12.9	Ethyl acetate	3.15
Benzene	2.95	Carbon disulphide	1.01
Cyclohexane	0.19		

amino acid is suggested to be the zwitterionic form (A).

The values of rate constant, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered as the complete range of the solvent parameters are not available), were correlated in terms of linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*⁹.

$$\log k = A + p\pi^* + \alpha\alpha + \beta\beta \quad (3)$$

Here π^* represents the solvent polarity for solvent-solute interaction of non-specific type, β is a scale of solvent hydrogen-bond acceptor basicity, while α represents the solvent hydrogen-bond donor acidity. A is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, for 13 solvents α has a value of zero. The analyses in terms of eq. (3), a two-parameter equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β gave the following results. Here n is the number of data points.

$$\log k_2 = -3.59 + 1.91 \pm 0.23 \pi^* + 0.22 \pm 0.19 \alpha - 0.19 \pm 0.18 \beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8613; sd = 0.22; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.64 + 1.98 \pm 0.22 \pi^* + 0.15 \pm 0.18 \beta \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8512; sd = 0.22; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.61 + 2.02 \pm 0.22 \pi^* \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8443; sd = 0.21; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.52 + 0.51 \pm 0.43 \beta \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0794; sd = 0.52; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

The results show that *ca.* 86% of data on solvent effect is

explained by eq. (3). According to Exner's criterion¹⁰, however, the correlation is poor. The major contribution is from the solvent polarity term, π^* . Both α and β play relatively insignificant roles. There is no significant collinearity between π^* and β for the eighteen solvents ($r^2 = 0.0477$, $sd = 0.24$).

The data on solvent effect were analysed also in terms of Swain's¹¹ eq. (8), where A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term, and $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity.

$$\log k = aA + bB + C \quad (8)$$

The results of the correlation analyses in terms of eq. (8), individually with A and B , and with $(A + B)$ are given below.

$$\log k_2 = 0.71 \pm 0.01 A + 2.05 \pm 0.01 B - 3.85 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9998; sd = 0.01; n = 19; \psi = 0.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.42 \pm 0.68 A - 3.56 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0218; sd = 0.55; n = 19; \psi = 1.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 2.00 \pm 0.13 B - 3.62 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9373; sd = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.26$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.60 \pm 0.17 (A + B) - 3.81 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8373; sd = 0.22; n = 19; \psi = 0.41$$

The data on solvent effect showed an excellent correlation in terms of Swain's eq. (8) with both anion- and cation-solvating powers contributing to the observed solvent effect. However, the role of cation-solvation is major and it alone accounts for *ca.* 94% of the data. There is no significant collinearity between A and B for the nineteen solvents ($r^2 = 0.0108$; $sd = 0.27$). The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$ accounted for 84% of the data. In view of the fact that 84% of data are accounted for by $(A + B)$, an attempt was made to correlate data with the relative permittivity of the solvents. A plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of relative permittivity, however, is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5108$).

The solvent polarity term of Kamlet's eq. (3) explained *ca.* 84% of the data. Thus, it seems that the solvent polarity terms of the two equations represent almost the same solvent property. This is borne out by the fact that there is a significant collinearity between π^* and $(A + B)$ for the eighteen solvents ($r^2 = 0.7811$).

The solvent effect suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. It seems that the carboxylate oxygen suffers an electrophilic attack by BTPPD. The increased polarity of the transition state is facilitated

by an increase in the ionising power of the solvent. This is justified by observed rate data.

Correlation analysis of reactivity :

The rates of oxidation of the amino acids show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* substituent constants¹², the reaction constants being negative (Table 5).

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \log k_0 \quad (13)$$

The values of the substituent constants were obtained from the compilations by Wiberg¹². The negative polar reaction constant suggests that the electron-releasing groups promote the reaction while electron-withdrawing groups retard the reaction.

Table 5. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant in the oxidation of amino acids by BTPPD

T (K)	ρ^*	R^2	sd	ψ	n^a
298	-0.59 ± 0.01	0.9990	0.005	0.034	9
308	-0.55 ± 0.01	0.9981	0.006	0.046	9
318	-0.48 ± 0.01	0.9995	0.003	0.024	9
328	-0.44 ± 0.01	0.9996	0.002	0.021	9

^aNo. of data points.

Mechanism : A one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. BHT is an excellent trap for free radicals¹³. The fact that BHT was recovered unchanged also goes against the occurrence of one-electron oxidation.

The absence of kinetic isotope effect suggested that the α -C-H-bond is not cleaved in the rate-determining step. The negative polar reaction constant suggested that the reactions are facilitated by electron releasing groups. An increase in the electron density at the carboxylate ion promotes the reaction. The low magnitude of reaction constant suggested that the reaction centre is not close to the site of substitution. Therefore, based on all above experimental data, two mechanisms are proposed - one involving an interaction between 2 moles of zwitterionic form of amino acid (A) and BTPPD and the second involving an interaction between 2A and BTPPDH₂⁺ in a pre-equilibrium stage, to form an intermediate complex. The complex then disproportionates in a slow step, to give a corresponding protonated aldimine (Schemes 1 and 2). In Scheme 1 protonation of the complex takes place prior to disproportionation. The above postulations are supported by the observed solvent effect indicating much more contribution of the cation-solvation. Though, the

R' = butyltriphenyl

Scheme 1

R' = butyltriphenyl

Scheme 2

formation of an intermediate complex is postulated in the oxidation of amino acid, the second order dependence on amino acid concentration can be explained by assuming that the value of the equilibrium constant, K_1 , is very small and is, therefore, not reflected in the rate law. It may be mentioned that though the formation of complex and its diprotonation are shown as single step each, these must be taking place in two steps each. The above mechanisms are supported by the observed parameters of activation. As the charge separation takes place in the transition state, the two charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules and is reflected in the loss in entropy.

Initially Cr^{VI} is reduced to Cr^{IV} . It is likely to react with another Cr^{VI} to generate Cr^{V} which is then reduced in a fast step to the ultimate product Cr^{III} . Such a sequence of reactions in Cr^{VI} oxidations is well known¹⁴.

Experimental

Materials :

BTPPD was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. All the amino acids were commercial products of highest degree of purity and were used as such. Perdeuteriogylicine (Dgly- $\text{ND}_2\text{CD}_2\text{COOD}$) was obtained from Sigma Chemicals (USA). Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionated. Toluene *p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis : The oxidation of amino acid leads to the formation of corresponding aldimines. The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, α -alanine (0.1 mol) and BTPPD (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml glacial acetic acid in the presence of 1.0 mol dm^{-3} of TsOH. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand in the dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The amount of aldimine formed was then determined by the reported 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine method¹⁵. In this method the aldimine is hydrolysed to the aldehyde and then isolated as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP). The product is then vacuum dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.01 g ($\approx 90\%$) and 1.77 g ($\approx 79\%$) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of acetaldehyde. In similar experiments, with the other amino acids the yields of

DNP, after recrystallization, were in the range of 66–79%.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, BTPPD (0.005 mol) and α -alanine (0.001 mol) were made up to 100 ml in glacial acetic acid in the presence of 1.0 mol dm^{-3} of TsOH. The reaction was allowed to stand for *ca.* 15 h to ensure the completion of reaction. The residual BTPPD was determined spectrophotometrically at 370 nm. Several determinations, with varying amounts of alanine showed that the stoichiometry is 3 : 1 i.e. 3 moles of amino acid are consumed by 1 mole of oxidant. Thus, BTPPD acts as 6-electron oxidant and reduced to Cr^{III} .

Kinetic measurements : Pseudo-first order conditions were attained by keeping a large excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the amino acid over oxidant. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$) and in flasks blackened from the outside to prevent any photochemical reaction. The solvent was glacial acetic acid. The reactions were followed iodometrically for up to 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [\text{BTPPD}]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The specific rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{amino acid}]^2 [\text{H}^+]^2$. In correlation analyses, we have used coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2), standard deviation (*sd*), and Exner's parameter¹⁰, ψ , as the measures of the goodness of fit.

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